

PERMEABILITY OF MULTI-POROUS MEDIA: NUMERICAL MODELLING AND VERIFICATION

M. Nordlund¹, T.S. Lundström¹

¹*Division of Fluid Mechanics, Luleå University of Technology
SE-971 87 Luleå, Sweden*

SUMMARY: Computational simulations are carried out in order to derive the importance of modelling multi-scale porosity for saturated permeability. Two unit cell models are developed for a biaxial Non-Crimp Fabric, one with solid fibre bundles and one with porous. Two autonomous methods are then used to derive the grid independent solution yielding that the predicted values are equal when the solution is in the asymptotic range. In addition a new method to study the convergence of the solution as a function of mesh density is suggested. It is finally found that the bundles only contribute with a few percentages to the total permeability.

KEYWORDS: CFD, Multi-porosity, Grid resolution, Permeability.

INTRODUCTION

There is a new trend of applying modelling- and simulation-based design methods in composite manufacturing in order to decrease time and costs and to obtain higher quality materials and processes. To exemplify, computational simulations have been used for permeability prediction models on both the micro scale level [1] and the meso scale level for various types of fabrics such as uni-directional- [2], woven- [3] and Non-crimp fabrics [4]. The simplicity to handle flow through complex geometries where analytical expressions gets complex or fail, is the major advantage of using computational simulations for solving for the flow field. The primary disadvantage, on the other hand, is the introduction of errors into the results due to the required discretization of the partial differential equations (PDEs) and from the iterative methods used to solve for the flow field. These errors make it necessary to always quantify the numerical accuracy and if possible compare the simulations with analytical models as in [5]. Invalid simulations results can have tremendous effects on the products and processes and result in high costs, bad quality, and erroneous process set-ups. The accuracy of the computational simulations is therefore an important issue when it comes to these design methods and the way to avoid these kinds of failures and to increase the reliability and confidence in modelling- and simulation-based designs, is by careful verification and validation. In [5], painstaking verification of a unit cell model of biaxial non-crimp fabrics (NCFs) was performed, where the numerical accuracy of the simulations was controlled together with comparison to analytical models. It was shown that the lack of grid independence can significantly influence the results.

There are a number of ways to verify the numerical accuracy of computational simulations. Richardson's extrapolation based methods [6] and Taylor expansion methods [7] can be used in order to determine the discretization error as well as comparison of variables and flow fields. Even though computational simulations are commonly used in composite manufacturing and methods exist to estimate the numerical errors, verification studies to secure the quality of the simulations are rarely used.

The importance of the multi-porous nature of NCFs has been debated, that is, whether or not the fibre bundles should be included when modelling the saturated permeability. In [8] it

was shown, that for unidirectional fabrics with cylindrical fibre bundles, the bundles are important when their permeability is comparable in magnitude with the permeability for a model with solid bundles. Hence, for certain fibre volume fractions in the bundles, they can be modelled as impermeable solids.

This paper presents a study of the importance of verification of computational simulations of multi-scale porosity media. The accuracy of Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) simulations of two unit cell models of a biaxial NCF are studied together with the importance of the dual scale porous nature of the NCF when determining the saturated permeability.

VERIFICATION AND VALIDATION IN CFD

In computational modelling and simulations the reality is modelled by a conceptual model, which consists of all the information, mathematical modelling data and mathematical equations that describe the physical system, cf. Fig. 1. The determination of the adequacy of the conceptual model for the intended application in CFD is generally called qualification [9]. The computerized model is the implementation of the conceptual model into a computer program and the control that a computerized model represents a conceptual model within specified limits of accuracy is called verification, Fig. 1. The validation on the other hand is rooted in the question how the computerized model represents the physical system in reality and is based on comparison with experimental observations. In this work the focus is set on the verification of the CFD simulations in order to develop a general trust in the modelling and design based methods in permeability prediction models where validation experiments are not available.

Fig. 1: Phases of modelling and simulation and the role of verification and validation [9].

Verification can be done by either analytical models as was done in [5] or by highly accurate simulations as in [4]. Analytical models can often be impossible to derive for complex systems, hence control of the numerical accuracy of the simulations is in these cases vital in order to verify the results from the computerized model. The 5 major sources of errors in CFD simulations are insufficient spatial discretization, insufficient temporal discretization, insufficient iterative convergence, computer round-off and computer programming errors [10]. Since the steady state flow problem in this work is solved by using a commercial software that is assumed to be well tested and double precision, the two major errors remaining to control are the spatial discretization and the iterative convergence error.

Iterative convergence error

The iterative convergence error evolves from the nature of the iterative procedure to solve the system of non-linear PDEs. For pure (time-independent) boundary value problems, the iterative convergence can be controlled by the residual errors that remain in the approximate solution to the different discrete equations. Residual vectors are computed for each iteration at every node and to measure the residual error over the entire domain, an appropriate vector norm is computed, which in this work is the root mean square (RMS) norm. The value of the RMS norm is then compared with previous iterations and a reduction of 3-5 decades is taken as a sign of iterative convergence [11]. Different parameters and variables have different iterative convergence and it is therefore important to control the specific variable of interest, in this case the permeability, even if the residuals show iterative convergence. The permeability, K , is defined by Darcy's law, which in its one dimensional form of can be written as [12]:

$$\frac{Q}{A} = \frac{K \Delta p}{\mu L}, \quad (1)$$

where Q is the flow rate, A is the total cell face area of the unit cell perpendicular to the flow direction, μ the dynamic viscosity, p the pressure and L the length of the unit cell.

Spatial discretization error

The spatial discretization error, E , arises from the discrete representation of the fluid domain and can be defined as:

$$E = \varphi_{exact} - \varphi_{discrete}, \quad (2)$$

where φ_{exact} is the mathematically correct solution of the exact PDEs of the conceptual model for a given set of boundary conditions and initial conditions. $\varphi_{discrete}$ is the numerical solution of a given discrete approximation of the same PDEs and conditions produced by the given code. The error, E , depends on the discretization and can be symbolized by a characteristic grid spacing h , which may be spatially varying through the domain and should approach zero as h approaches zero, exclusive of the computer round-off errors. The estimation of E can, by using the triangle inequality, be written as [10]:

$$E \leq \|\varphi_{exact} - \varphi_{h \rightarrow 0}\| + \|\varphi_{h \rightarrow 0} - \varphi_{h,I,c}\| < \varepsilon, \quad (3)$$

where $\varphi_{h \rightarrow 0}$ is the limit of the exact solution of the discrete mapping of the PDEs and their initial and boundary conditions and $\varphi_{h,I,c}$ is the discrete solution using a given algorithm for a finite spatial grid spacing h , iterative convergence parameter I and computer c and ε is an arbitrary small number, typically the choice of accuracy bound for the simulation. The first term in Eqn. (3) is the error introduced by the exact solution of the discrete equations. Generally, for relatively simple flows and simple spatial discretization schemes, this term is zero [10]. The second term on the other hand is the primary reason for performing calculation verification. This term will be non-zero due to the finite h , I , finite precision arithmetic and programming errors and can even be large due to computing resource limitations. The calculation verification is consequently concentrated on bounding $\|\varphi_{h \rightarrow 0} - \varphi_{h,I,c}\|$ as precisely as possible for the specific problem. Two methods are used in this work in order to determine the grid independent permeability and furthermore also the grid dependence of the simulation results.

Richardson's extrapolation method with an observed order of convergence

The first assumption in order to perform Richardson's extrapolation is that φ a smooth solution of the exact PDEs. Secondly, the formal order of convergence n of the spatial discretization method is known and third and last that the mesh spacing is small enough so that the leading-order error term dominates the total discretization error. In this case the order of accuracy is constant as the grid size is reduced beyond a specific threshold and the discretization is said to be in the asymptotic range [10]. The exact solution can then, for a steady-state computational problem in one spatial dimension with uniform mesh spacing h , be expanded as:

$$\varphi_{exact}(\vec{x}) = \varphi_h(\vec{x}) + \alpha h^n + O(h^{n+1}), \quad (4)$$

where α is a constant. The convergence rate, n , is usually not known and the second assumption has therefore to be relaxed. In case the spatial grid size varies over the domain of the discretization, the estimate of n represents a local- rather than a global-estimate. The three unknowns can be calculated by using three numerical solutions with different grid spacing h_1 , h_2 and h_3 respectively. The grid spacings for the three grids can be written in terms of h , as: $h_1 = \beta_1 h$, $h_2 = \beta_2 h$ and $h_3 = \beta_3 h$, where $\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3$ are grid refinement factors given by:

$$\beta_j = \left(\frac{N_f}{N_j} \right)^{1/3}, \quad (5)$$

where N_f is the number of elements for the finest grid and N_j for the coarser grids. Using Eqn. (4) for the three grids, the observed order of convergence n can be calculated from:

$$\frac{\varphi_{h_2} - \varphi_{h_3}}{\varphi_{h_1} - \varphi_{h_2}} = \frac{\beta_3^n - \beta_2^n}{\beta_2^n - \beta_1^n}, \quad (6)$$

and furthermore also the extrapolated value of φ by:

$$\phi_{extrapolated} = \frac{\beta_1^n \varphi_{h_2} - \beta_2^n \varphi_{h_1}}{\beta_1^n - \beta_2^n}. \quad (7)$$

Taylor expansion method with mixed order of convergence

In [7] another approach to calculate the grid independent solution is used. This method relaxes the assumption that the solutions have to be in the asymptotic region of convergence and it is assumed that both the first- and second-order errors are present in the discretization error for the specified grid resolutions. In order to estimate the converged solution, three different grids are required to solve for the three unknowns, as for the previous method. The converged solution is expanded as:

$$\varphi_{exact}(\vec{x}) = \varphi_h(\vec{x}) + g_1 h + g_2 h^2 + O(h^3). \quad (8)$$

Independent of the method used to calculate the grid independent value, it is important to realize that different variables and functionals converge at different rates as for the iterative

convergence. Hence, it is important to perform the grid convergence study with respect to the variables or functionals of interest for the problem, which in this work is the permeability.

MODELLING AND SIMULATION

Biaxial NCFs consist of layers of parallel fibre bundles, preferable in different directions, stitched together. The typical length scales of the flow geometry when impregnating the fabric are $<10\mu\text{m}$ in the fibre bundles and $>100\mu\text{m}$ in the inter-bundle channels. Two unit cell models of a biaxial NCF, fabric 2 in [12] are developed. The first unit cell model, the *porous model* includes both the porous fibre bundles and the inter-bundle channels, Fig. 2(a). The second unit cell model, the *channel model* developed in [4, 5], excludes the fibre bundles and treat them as solids. The fluid domain therefore solely consists of the inter-bundle channels, Fig. 2(b).

Fig. 2: One fourth of the unit cell a) including and b) excluding the porous fibre bundles.

The finite volume based method used to solve the incompressible, Newtonian, steady state, laminar flow ($\text{Re} \ll 1$) in the present work is CFD with the software Ansys CFX5.7.1. A second-order differencing scheme is used for the discretization of the equations solved by the multi-grid solver: the Navier-Stokes equation and the continuity equation in the forms:

$$\rho \frac{\partial \bar{u}}{\partial t} + \rho \bar{u} \cdot \nabla \bar{u} = -\nabla p + \mu \nabla^2 \bar{u} + \nabla p_{\text{applied}} - \frac{\mu}{K} \bar{u}, \quad (9)$$

$$\nabla \bar{u} = 0, \quad (10)$$

where ρ is the fluid density and \bar{u} the fluid velocity and $\nabla p_{\text{applied}}$ the applied pressure gradient to drive the flow. In the inter-bundle channels region, the last term in Eqn. (9) is zero while in the porous fibre bundles regions, K depends on the fibre direction. The directional fibre bundle permeability can be calculated by [13]:

$$K_{\parallel} = \frac{8}{53} \frac{(1 - V_{f \text{ bundle}})^3}{V_{f \text{ bundle}}^2} R^2 \quad \text{and} \quad (11)$$

$$K_{\perp} = \frac{16}{9\sqrt{6}\pi} \left(\frac{\pi}{2\sqrt{3}V_{f \text{ bundle}}} - 1 \right)^{5/2} R^2, \quad (12)$$

for hexagonal fibre arrangement. K_{\parallel} and K_{\perp} are the permeability parallel and perpendicular to the fibres respectively, $V_{f \text{ bundle}}$ is the fibre volume fraction within the bundles and R is the

fibre radius. Five fibre volume fractions are used, $V_{f\ bundle} \in [0.250\ 0.375\ 0.500\ 0.625\ 0.750]$, for a fibre radius of $7\ \mu\text{m}$ in order to study the differences in their convergence behaviour. Periodic boundary conditions are set on the unit cell faces perpendicular to the applied pressure gradient in order to simulate the periodic behaviour of the unit cell. Symmetry is furthermore used to reduce the computational cell to one fourth of the actual unit cell, cf. Fig. 2(a), (b). No-slip boundary condition is set on the bundles for the *channel model* and a continuous flow condition for the *porous model*.

Nine tetrahedral grids are produced by Ansys ICEM CFD for the *porous model*, cf. Table 1 and 14 grids for the *channel model*, cf. Table 2. The advantage with the *channel model* is that a higher volume element density, $\rho_{v.e.}$, can be achieved, due to the reduced fluid domain.

Table 1: Grid information for the porous model.

Grid	No. of nodes	$\rho_{v.e.} [v.e./mm^3]$
P-1	12384	26829
P-2	19539	42415
P-3	28940	64861
P-4	50180	116835
P-5	99820	234563
P-6	139851	325653
P-7	189175	443315
P-8	278142	661079
P-9	425872	1021024

Table 2: Grid information for the channel model.

Grid	No. of nodes	$\rho_{v.e.} [v.e./mm^3]$
C-1	2246	28209
C-2	3365	45102
C-3	4882	69615
C-4	7880	115521
C-5	14746	229161
C-6	19049	306482
C-7	27539	442469
C-8	40420	669782
C-9	60971	1037638
C-10	100475	1755580
C-11	187192	3362037
C-12	331721	5853444
C-13	536194	9546476
C-14	1012943	18335755

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

The iterative convergence is controlled by a reduction of the RMS residual norms more than 4 decades together with the convergence of the permeability. As seen in Fig. 3(a) and (b), the permeability converges quickly with the iteration number for all grid sizes tested for the two models.

Fig. 3: The iterative convergence of K for (a) the porous model with $V_{f\ bundle}=50\%$ and (b) the channel model.

The grid convergences for the *porous model* for the five porosities of the fibre bundles and the *channel model* are studied in order to investigate the convergence behaviour of different dual scale porosities. The grid convergence behaviour of the permeability proves to be strictly grid dependent and more or less independent of the bundle fibre volume fraction, cf. Fig. 4(a). Fig. 4(b) shows that the alteration in the permeability for the *channel model* is large for small values of $\rho_{v.e.}$ but flattens out after about 2 million $v.e./mm^3$.

Fig. 4: Grid convergence behaviour of (a) the porous model with different fibre volume fractions of the fibre bundles and (b) the channel model.

In order to compare the convergence behaviours between the two unit cell models, the velocity gradient resolution is calculated for all the grids. The parameter:

$$\xi = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^3 \left(\max \left(\frac{|u_{grad,i}^{(j)}| l_e^{(j)}}{|\Delta(u_{grad,i})|} \right) \right)^2}, \quad (13)$$

is used as a measure of the gradient resolution where $l_e^{(j)}$ is the mean element length at node j and $\Delta(u_{grad,i})$ is the global range of the velocity gradient in the i -direction. As seen in the zoomed part of Fig. 5, the ξ -convergences for the *porous model* for all V_f bundle seem to be nearly identical and also similar to the convergence for the *channel model*. Fig. 5 also shows that the ξ -gradient flattens out and reaches a nearly constant value after approximately 5000000 $v.e./mm^3$ for the *channel model*. The grids of the *porous model* never reach this grid

resolution, due to its larger fluid domain and resulting high computer memory requirement. The grids therefore remain in the region of large ζ -changes.

Fig. 5: The convergences of ζ for the two unit cell models.

The three grids with highest $\rho_{v.e}$ for the two unit cell methods are used in order to calculate the grid independent permeability with both *Richardson's extrapolation method with an observed order of convergence*, K_{REM} , and the *Taylor expansion method with mixed order of convergence*, K_{TEM} . The high value ($n > 2$) for the *porous model* with $V_{f\ bundle} \in [0.375\ 0.500\ 0.625\ 0.750]$ indicates that the three grids are not in the asymptotic region of convergence, Table 3. This can also be understood since the three grids used are in the region where the ζ -gradient changes a lot ($\rho_{v.e.} < 5000000\ v.e./mm^3$), cf. Fig. 5. The large differences in the grid independent permeability calculated by the two methods, K_{REM} and K_{TEM} for the *porous model* for these $V_{f\ bundle}$:s, also contribute to the indications that there is a lack of asymptotic convergence for the grids. $V_{f\ bundle} = 0.250$ is the only fibre volume fraction, which show an observed order of convergence indicating asymptotic behaviour ($1 \leq n \leq 2$), but on the other hand the large changes in the ζ -gradient in Fig. 5 indicates that care should be taken before assuming the grids are in the asymptotic region. Higher $\rho_{v.e.}$ is required for the *porous model*, regardless of $V_{f\ bundle}$ s, in order to reach the region of a nearly constant ζ -gradient. For the *channel model*, n indicates an asymptotic behaviour which is also supported by the nearly constant ζ -gradient for the three grids, cf. Fig. 5. For the model with the solid bundles, the values of K_{REM} and K_{TEM} are almost identical.

Table 3: Grid independent permeability and observed order of convergence.

$V_{f\ bundle}$ [%]	N	K_{REM} [m ²]	K_{TEM} [m ²]
25.0	1.76	$1.991 \cdot 10^{-10}$	$1.998 \cdot 10^{-10}$
37.5	4.02	$1.614 \cdot 10^{-10}$	$1.534 \cdot 10^{-10}$
50.0	4.79	$1.516 \cdot 10^{-10}$	$1.416 \cdot 10^{-10}$
62.5	4.96	$1.485 \cdot 10^{-10}$	$1.385 \cdot 10^{-10}$
75.0	4.83	$1.473 \cdot 10^{-10}$	$1.376 \cdot 10^{-10}$
Solid	1.54	$1.477 \cdot 10^{-10}$	$1.474 \cdot 10^{-10}$

Since the three finest grids for the channel model are in the asymptotic region of convergence, the extrapolated value of the *channel model* can be used to calculate how far from grid independence the grids are. The permeability with grid C-1 is ~37% from grid independence while it is 0.88% for grid C-14. Control of the numerical accuracy is therefore crucial for accurate permeability prediction.

Since the grid convergences for the two models approach the grid independent permeability from two different directions, cf. Fig. 4(a), (b), it is important to perform verification in order to know if and when the fibre bundles can be neglected in saturated permeability models. As Fig. 6 indicates, incorrect conclusions can be drawn when grid convergence is not established. For example, the *porous model* with $V_{f\ bundle} = 75\%$ show large deviation between the two models for coarse grids, while their permeability actually converges as the grids are refined, which is in agreement with the observations in [8] for uni-directional fabrics. Another example is for $V_{f\ bundle} = 25\%$ at grid 4 it seems that the two models give similar permeability prediction, while for finer grids the difference between the two models is considerable. These two examples emphasize the importance of verification and control of the grid convergence in order to avoid erroneous assumptions multi-porous media.

Fig. 6: Difference in permeability between the channel model and the porous model for the 9 coarsest grids.

CONCLUSIONS

In this work a verification study of the permeability prediction accuracy of a biaxial NCF is performed. It is shown that verification of the computational simulations is absolutely necessary for accurate permeability predictions of the unit cells of the fabric. It is furthermore also proved that grid independence is crucial in studies of the importance of the multi-scale porosity for saturated permeability predictions models, where lack of grid independence can lead to negligence of the fibre bundles where they are important. The observed order of convergence calculated by the Richardson's extrapolated method is a good indicator of asymptotic convergence behaviour, but it is also shown that a study of the grid resolution convergence is an important help in the determination of the asymptotic region. The two methods: *Richardson's extrapolation method with an observed order of convergence* and the *Taylor expansion method with mixed order of convergence* give approximately the same grid independent permeability if the grids all are in the asymptotic range, while they give different values for grids outside the asymptotic region.

REFERENCES

1. Ngo, N.D. and Tamma, K.K., "Microscale permeability predictions of porous fibrous media", *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer*, Vol. 44, 2001, pp. 3135-3145.
2. Ranganathan, S., Phelan JR., F.R. and Advani, S.G., "A generalized model for the transverse fluid permeability in unidirectional fibrous media", *Polymer composites*, Vol. 17, No. 2, 1996, pp. 222-230.
3. Song, Y.S., Chung, T.J., Kang, T.J. and Youn, J.R., "Prediction of permeability tensor for three dimensional circular braided perform by applying a finite volume method to a unit cell", *Composites Science and Technology*, Vol. 64, 2004, pp. 1629-1636.
4. Nordlund, M. and Lundström, T.S., "Numerical Study of the Local Permeability of Non-Crimp Fabrics", *Journal of Composite Materials*, Vol. 39, No. 10, 2005, **In print**.
5. Nordlund, M. and Lundström, T.S., "Numerical Calculations of the Permeability of Non-Crimp Fabrics", *Proceedings of ICCM-14 Conference*. San Diego, California, USA, July 14-18, 2003.
6. Celik, I. and Zhang, W.M., "Calculation of numerical uncertainty using richardson extrapolation: Application to some simple turbulent flow calculations", *Journal of Fluids Engineering*, Vol. 117, 1995, pp. 439-445.
7. Roy, C.J., McWherter-Payne, M.A. and Oberkampf, W.L., "Verification and validation for laminar hypersonic flows", *AIAA*, 2000, pp. 2000-2550.
8. Pillai, K.M. and Advani, S.G., "Numerical and analytical study to estimate the effect of two length scales upon permeability of a fibrous porous medium", *Transport in Porous Media*, Vol. 21, 1995, pp. 1-17.
9. Schlesinger, S., "Terminology for model credibility", *Simulation*, Vol. 32, No. 11, 1979, pp. 103-104.
10. Oberkampf, W.L. and Trucano, T.G., "Verification and validation in computational fluid dynamics", *Progress in Aerospace Sciences*, Vol. 38, 2002, pp. 209-272.
11. Roache, P.J., "Quantification of uncertainty in computational fluid dynamics", *Annual Review of Fluid Mechanics*, Vol. 29, 1997, pp. 123-160.
12. Lundström, T.S., "The permeability of non-crimp-stitched fabrics", *Composites: Part A*, Vol. 31, 2000, pp. 1345-1353.
13. Gebart, B.R., "Permeability of unidirectional reinforcements for RTM", *Journal of Composite Materials*, Vol. 26, 1992, pp.1100-1133.